

1 News/Views article:

2 **Title:**

3 **Digital health technologies need regulation and reimbursement that**
4 **enable flexible interactions and groupings**

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12 **Abstract**

13 **Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) are being applied in a widening range of scenarios in**
14 **medicine. We describe the emerging phenomenon of the grouping of individual DHTs,**
15 **with a clinical use case and regulatory approval in their own right, into packages to**
16 **perform specific clinical tasks in defined settings. Example groupings include suites of**
17 **devices for remote monitoring, or for smart clinics. In this first article of a two-article**
18 **series, we describe challenges in implementation and limitations in frameworks for the**
19 **regulation, health technology assessment, and reimbursement of these device suites**
20 **and linked novel care pathways.**

21 **[MAIN]**

22 Digital health technologies (DHTs) include wearables and devices for mobile health
23 (mHealth), health information technology (IT), telehealth and telemedicine, and personalized
24 medicine^{1,2}. There is a global trend for the greater utilization of these technologies in medical
25 practice, however there are substantial national differences in how they are perceived,
26 evaluated for regulatory approval, and reimbursed or otherwise compensated³. DHTs will
27 play an increasing role in the economic affordability and environmental sustainability of
28 healthcare systems with the capacity to meet societal needs that were previously
29 unaddressed^{4,5}. By offering customized, adaptable care solutions, they hold the potential to
30 facilitate safer and more extensive home-based and local care while empowering patients to
31 actively engage in their health management⁶. In this first article in a two-article series, we
32 describe the new phenomenon of flexible suites of DHTs, the current applicable regulatory
33 and HTA frameworks, and their application during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the second
34 article of the series, we describe what new frameworks could include.

35

36 Since the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been increasing bundling of individual DHTs,
37 which have specified intended medical purposes and associated approvals, into suites to
38 deliver aggregated 'intended purposes' in some cases different from those of any individual
39 component device. The complexity of the interactions between devices within suites, and of
40 suites with one another, can deliver new paradigms of medical treatment but may also
41 produce unexpected "emergent" actions or properties. Sets of DHTs can have differing
42 levels of workflow integration with telemedicine and with the electronic health record (EHR).
43 Examples of services delivered through device-aggregates of DHTs are: groupings of
44 remote passive and active sensor systems, automated monitoring platforms, alarms and
45 teleconsultation platforms to: (i) allow Health Care Providers (HCP) to monitor chronically ill
46 patients at home⁴; (ii) enable Hospital-at-Home programs (HaH)⁷ (iii) improve treatment
47 efficiency in hospital or care home settings^{8,9}; and, (iv) enable 'smart clinics' with physical
48 exams by remote clinicians via the patient or their family in their own home by the use of

49 mHealth platforms and wireless thermometers, stethoscopes, otoscopes and
50 laryngoscopes¹⁰ (**Figure 1**). We examine the challenges posed by the implementation,
51 evaluation, and assessment of interactions within grouped systems of networked devices for
52 regulatory and health technology assessment (HTA) purposes.

53

54 [Figure 1]

55

56 **Have grouped devices not always existed?**

57 On one level, the ad hoc grouping together of separate medical devices which were
58 developed by different manufactures is a long-standing practice. For example, an orthopedic
59 surgeon's preferred instruments and/or implants of, are often grouped and sterilized
60 together, in racks or trays. In some cases, such groupings were brought together, and
61 regulated together as 'procedure packs'¹³. A key difference between 'sets' of such
62 'traditional' medical devices and aggregations of DHTs, is that the latter are used to build a
63 suite of networked interconnected devices, which have complex data flows and resultant
64 dynamic dependencies between each other. While many suites continue to be reliant on
65 healthcare staff for operation, there is realistic potential for transitioning to greater
66 automation and use of these as aggregated 'super devices' with limited human intervention
67 in the future.

68

69 **The HaH concept as an example of the evolution of DHT/HCP aggregate system**

70 As described in **Figure 1**, the Hospital at Home (HaH) suite generally consists of aggregated
71 health sensors, alert systems, smart pill boxes, systems for continuous remote monitoring
72 and remote digital patient support. This application is already used to treat patients, so by
73 definition, there already are processes in place for its regulation. Although the HaH concept
74 existed before the COVID-19 pandemic, it was during the pandemic that the concept gained
75 traction in the UK and several other countries¹⁴. This was due, at least in part, to temporary

76 regulation, and reimbursement changes globally. In the US, the Centers for Medicare and
77 Medicaid Services (CMS), allowed for the reimbursement of HAH care as a diagnosis-
78 related group (DRG) as well as waived certain previously mandatory requirements for
79 remote patient monitoring¹⁵. Other regulatory changes included encouraging adoption of
80 telehealth and remote consulting, allowing for remote acquisition of data, along with fast-
81 tracking of trials and of the entry of vaccines into the market^{16,17}. European countries that
82 have applied the HaH model are the UK, US, Spain, The Netherlands, Canada and
83 Australia, and there has also been early adoption in many other EU countries⁷. In the US,
84 the CMS has extended the acute HaH program, initiated in 2019 during the pandemic, until
85 Dec 2024 to further evaluate the benefits of HAH, marking a pioneering step towards
86 telehealth adoption¹⁸. A 2023 early value assessment by the National Institute for Health
87 and Care Excellence (NICE), in the UK, supported the potential cost-effectiveness of HAH or
88 virtual wards, while acknowledging the remaining uncertainty and need for further evidence
89 generation. That review also highlighted assessment challenges such as insufficient prior
90 data, a lack of suitable comparators, interactions across diverse policies, variations in the
91 standard of care, and overall heterogeneity^{19,20}. However, suited to the rapid pace of digital
92 innovation, NICE's conditional approval supported both the ability to safely generate further
93 evidence and the addressing of unmet patient needs.

94

95 **Challenges for adoption and evaluation of DHT suites**

96 There are safety and performance challenges with grouping of DHTs, especially those built
97 up of individual medical device (MD) and non-MD DHTs, due to networked-device
98 interactions, and other emergent system properties²¹. Ensuring interoperability and
99 applicability across various demographics poses significant hurdles, necessitating thorough
100 examination of each system component. Cybersecurity of individual components and of the
101 aggregated system of DHTs, including of internet of medical things devices (IoMT, e.g.,
102 sensors) requires careful regulatory attention, particularly for systems that will form part of

103 clinical health delivery infrastructure, such as HaH services, as the broader risks they pose
104 could extend beyond individual patients and threaten the integrity of entire healthcare
105 systems²². Many DHTs are adaptive, either through agile software refinements, or the
106 ongoing training of artificial intelligence models, and this brings additional complexity²³.
107 In the EU, medical device regulations require that systems of medical devices (MD) and non-
108 MD DHTs provided by commercial providers be treated as MDs by regulatory authorities²⁴
109 (Article 22). The commercial provider must then specifically risk assess all components, with
110 the provision of clinical data for the combination²⁵. Based on this, the interpretation of EU law
111 could suggest that manufacturers incorporating built-in smartphone/smartwatch components
112 like ECG sensors might require MD approval for all components, even those they don't
113 produce themselves, which could be impractical given their non-manufacturer status.
114 Guidance attempts clarification but burdens app developers with assessing and providing
115 evidence for every sensor configuration, a daunting task given the multitude of smartphone
116 brands and sensors²⁵. However, as the flexibility and variability of clinical settings in which
117 devices may be grouped into suites increases, it is valid to ask the question, of whether the
118 only model that could deliver benefit and safety for patients is requiring developers to
119 anticipate and test for every possible scenario of interaction. Reimbursement of such
120 systems also presents a challenge. Assessing cost-effectiveness and gathering evidence
121 for extensive modular DHT suites introduces new complexities. These include the absence
122 of comparators and the complex estimation of initial investments required for staff training
123 and system development²⁰.

124

125 **Summary**

126 Much of the transformation that will come from DHTs in increasing the quality and efficiency
127 of care will come from novel suites of DHTs in interactive 'fuzzy' care networks with HCPs,
128 and not from individual DHTs. In the US, the Center for Devices and Radiological Health
129 (CDRH) is actively working on forward thinking strategies for a regulatory pathway that

130 integrates this line of thought²⁶. There will be further maturation of the concept of suites of
131 DHTs, and further economic evaluations of these concepts. Although temporary adaptations
132 of regulatory and HTA frameworks served well in the pandemic, there is an opportunity to
133 explore whether new frameworks, and even new paradigms can be developed for the novel
134 scenario of complex multi-device digital/human workflows. We will address the question of
135 what new frameworks could include in the second article in this two-article series²⁷.

136

137 **Contributions**

138 S.G. developed the concept of the manuscript. R.M. wrote the first draft of the manuscript. R.M.,
139 P.M., A.C. and S.G. contributed to the writing, interpretation of the content, and editing of the
140 manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content. R.M., P.M., A.C. and S.G. had
141 final approval of the completed version. R.M., P.M., A.C. and S.G. take accountability for all
142 aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of
143 the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

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146 **Competing interests**

147 R.M and P.M. declare no nonfinancial interests and no competing financial interests. S.G.
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173

174 **Figure legends**

175 **Figure 1. Overview of modular DHT use across different healthcare settings.** Examples of
176 emerging approaches in the international adoption of suites of DHT devices are shown, along
177 with their component devices, applicable regulatory and HTA frameworks¹¹. The frameworks
178 are described for Germany, which has a statutory health insurance system, and a novel
179 reimbursement strategy for digital applications¹². Each circle represents a different healthcare

180 setting, with icons inside representing various DHTs that could be grouped to interact within that
181 setting. The colors around the icons signify reimbursement status in Germany: green for often
182 reimbursed, yellow for possible reimbursement, and blue for not usually reimbursed. Dotted
183 lines illustrate potential connectivity between devices, healthcare settings, electronic health
184 records, and AI tools. The red crosses indicate a lack of interoperability between these systems,
185 highlighting the need for improved connectivity and interoperability for comprehensive patient
186 health records and treatment decisions.

187

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266

MD Medical Device (according to Medical Regulatory guidelines)
 ~~MD~~ Not a medical Device (according to Medical Regulatory guidelines)
CDS- Clinical Decision Support (including Diagnostic/Therapeutic systems)

MD? May or may not be a Medical Device (evaluated case by case according to Medical Regulatory guidelines)
 ✗ Often lack of interoperability between healthcare settings
EHR - Electronic Health Record

ICU - Intensive Care Unit